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**ABOUT VALUE AND STUDY OF THE VARIOUS RISK FACTORS FOR
THE DEVELOPMENT OF A CEREBRAL STROKE**

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Abstract. Regional registers of strokes, heart attacks, and transient ischemic attacks are compiled in a uniform pattern in different countries of the world since the 1970s. They allow conducting epidemiological studies, studying the risk factors for cerebral strokes, developing and adjusting treatment, prevention and rehabilitation schemes for victims, and conducting prospective cohort studies.

Keywords: cardiovascular diseases, cerebral stroke, risk factors, history of stroke studies, Andersen-Fabry disease, epidemiology of strokes.

The problem of cerebral stroke remains of extreme social and medical importance throughout the world for several decades due to the high mortality rate, significant disability and social maladaptation of patients who have suffered it [1]. According to international epidemiological studies, in most countries, stroke occupies the second or third place in the structure of general mortality. According to WHO, stroke is a leading cause of disability in the adult population [2].

Risk factors for cerebral stroke are divided into behavioral (hypodynamia, smoking, alcohol abuse, overeating fats, sugar and salt, refusal to undergo a medical examination and the necessary correction of arterial hypertension, hypercholesterolemia, hyperglycemia, hyperhemoglobinemia, high-performance sports, living in areas where qualified medical care is not available), physiological / pathophysiological (distress, arterial hypertension, cardiac arrhythmias and conduction disorders, obesity, diabetes mellitus, age 60+, myocardial infarction, transient ischemic attacks and stroke in Anamnesis vitae, sleep apnea [3], thromboembolic diseases), genetic (Andersen-Farby disease, transient ischemic attacks and stroke in a Family anamnesis), environmental.

It is possible to classify risk factors with another grouping:

- biological, not subject to the influence of exogenous conditions (age, gender); endogenous (arterial hypertension, hypercholesterolemia); environmental factors and lifestyle (smoking, nutrition, physical activity); pathophysiological (changes on the ECG) (Stamler J., 1973);
- factors causing the disease (psycho-emotional, genetic, alimentary), contributing to the occurrence of the disease (constitutional features, age, occupational harmfulness), as well as enhancing or accelerating the process of its development (arterial hypertension, intoxication).
- initiators (giving rise to the disease); activators (contributing to its distribution); potentiators (enhancing its progression); precipitators (accelerating its development) (Houppkins P., 1981)
- internal (biological: gender, age, constitutional features, heredity, type of higher nervous activity) and external (natural and social: geographical, climatic, environmental, occupational factors, lifestyle characteristics, etc.) [4].

In the first place in terms of importance are behavioral risk factors. They are considered "correctable" or "managed." In second place are environmental factors and genetic factors (heredity). On the third – the possibilities of the health care system in a timely manner to establish a diagnosis and provide the necessary medical care in the early stages after a vascular catastrophe, and in the long run to prevent

repeated incidents and to carry out full rehabilitation of the victims [5]. Such a distribution of the queues of the influence of risk factors on cerebral strokes is consistent with WHO's ideas about the influence of various factors on all aspects of human health [6]: genetics – 20%, ecology – 20%, lifestyle – 50%, healthcare system – 10%. For Ukraine, the ratio of the influence of groups remains true, but the share of the influence of environmental factors [7; 8] and the health care system [9; 10] is increasing, due to the deplorable state of both directions. Different researchers often talk about a paradigm shift in health effects [11], but, in our opinion, it can be left without an average value changes.

Behavioral risk factors are well understood. Data on environmental factors are only accumulating. In large cities with developed industry, it is possible to establish a relationship between cerebral strokes and some air pollutants. For example, Yashnikova M.V. (2009) [12] shows the relationship of stroke and nitrogen dioxide (medium correlation force).

Genetic risk factors for stroke are also being actively studied. However, in some cases, this process drags on for decades. Especially if during this entire period it is possible to study only a few hundred cases of rare diseases (1200 cases of Anderson-Farby disease, for example). In Anderson-Fabry disease due to the accumulation of sphingolipids, transient ischemic attacks and strokes often occur [13]. It is difficult to recognize the disease if the pain is not severe. Suspect the existence of a stroke at a young age without obvious common risk factors [14]. The disease is dominant according to the type of inheritance – X-linked (with transmission from father to son or to daughter with mosaic genes), according to the pathogenetic mechanism – lysosomal storage disease (with accumulation of sphingolipids). Impaired sphingolipid metabolism is associated with a mutation in the GLA gene on the long arm of Xq22, which leads to congenital deficiency of α -galactosidase A (α -galA), to a cascade of ischemia and tissue fibrosis. The prevalence of the disease is 1: 40-480 thousand people [15]. In the pathogenesis of strokes in Anderson-Farby disease, a number of factors are associated with the accumulation of sphingolipids in the brain tissues, a number - with an altered state of the vessels. Magnetic resonance imaging

can detect changes in gray and white matter, as well as vascular malformations (most often dolichoectasis of the vertebrobasilar artery) [16].

Studying the risk factors for cerebral stroke is an important part of epidemiological studies. For such studies, in 1971, WHO organized the MONICA multicenter study in 12 countries worldwide, which covered 2.6 million stroke patients [17].

The register of stroke allows you to study [18]:

- incidence – the number of new cases of stroke per 1000 inhabitants of the studied region per year;
- prevalence – the number of primary and repeated strokes per 1000 inhabitants of the studied region per year [19];
- mortality – the number of stroke cases that ended fatally in the acute period of the disease (28 days) per 1000 or 100,000 residents of the studied region per year;
- death rate – the proportion of stroke cases ending fatally with respect to all recorded stroke cases in the study region;
- medical and socio-economic consequences of a stroke.

Stroke registers help develop prevention strategies. MONIKA multinational monitoring also made it possible to compare populations of different countries among themselves. At the second stage of the study, 15M stroke cases in 26 countries were analyzed, and it was concluded that routine statistics do not always adequately reflect the real state of the problem and require a critical attitude [17]. With each new stage of the study, the value and completeness of the data obtained increased. The findings of multicenter studies have become the basis for numerous regional and national registries for many decades to come.

Modern registries (for example, LIS-1, LIS-2 and LIS-3) often contain data about patients with heart attacks, strokes and transient ischemic attacks simultaneously [20; 21] allows you to evaluate the effectiveness of the selected treatment regimens, improve the preventive, curative and rehabilitation services, and the amount of data in them significantly exceeds the amount of data first studies. Collecting routine statistics is the responsibility of every MD who treats strokes. These statistics are

both a report on the work done and a source of new information for all those who work with registers and participate in prospective cohort studies.

REFERENCES

1. Stroke. Manual for Doctors / Ed. L.V. Stakhovskaya, S.V. Kotova. – M.: MIA Publishing House LLC, 2014. – 400 p. – ISBN 5998601538. URL: <https://medbook.ru/books/814>
2. 10 leading causes of death in the world // WHO, May 24, 2018. URL: <https://www.who.int/en/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/the-top-10-causes-of-death> (In Russian)
3. Frija-Orvoën E. Obstructive sleep apnea syndrome: Metabolic complications / E. Frija-Orvoën // Revue Des Maladies Respiratoires (ISSN 1776-2588). – 2016. – Vol. 33, No. 6. – P. 474-483. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rmr.2015.11.014>
4. Risk factors and their interconnection with cardio-vascular diseases: Chapter 1 in: Guidelines for cardiology // Clinical guidelines “Compendium”. URL: <https://compendium.com.ua/clinical-guidelines/cardiology/section-4/glava-1-factory-riska-i-ih-vzaimosvyaz-s-serdechno-sosudistymi-zabolevaniyami> (In Russian)
5. Yakhno N.N. Diseases of the nervous system / N.N. Yakhno, D.R. Shtulman, P.V. Melnichuk. – M., 1995. – Vol. 1. – 656 p. URL: <https://www.booksmed.com/nevrologiya/878-bolezni-nervnoj-sistemy-yaxno-shtulman.html> (In Russian)
6. Health for all by 2000 – a global strategy. – Geneva: WHO, 1981. – 104 p. (with appl.) URL: <https://apps.who.int/iris/handle/10665/201391> (In Russian)
7. Golubeva E. How to stop the transformation of Ukraine into a landfill? // Analytical and news portal 112.ua, July 19, 2017. URL: <https://112.ua/mnenie/kak-ostanovit-prevrashhenie-ukrainy-v-svalku-401827.html> (In Russian)
8. Oniliogvu E., Viskub O. What is the situation with open environmental monitoring data in Ukraine, what to do with it and where to go next? // Economic truth, July 17, 2018. URL: <https://www.epravda.com.ua/eng/columns/2018/07/17/638718> (In Ukrainian)

9. Klantsa A. Crisis determinants of health protection and their potential threat for the national security of the state / A. Klantsa // Public administration effectiveness: Collection of scientific papers of the Lviv Regional Institute of Public Administration of the National Academy of Public Administration at the President of Ukraine (ISSN 2070-4011). – 2018. – Vol. 55, No. 2, part 1. – P. 117-126. <https://doi.org/10.33990/2070-4011.55.2018.146722> (In Ukrainian)
10. Troyan M.Yu. Organizational and economic directions of reforming the healthcare system in Ukraine on the way out of the demographic crisis / M.Yu. Troyan, N.N. Kostyuchenko // The mechanism of regulation of the economy: International scientific journal (ISSN 1726-8699). – 2015. – No. 1. – P. 116-126. URL: http://mer.fem.sumdu.edu.ua/content/acticles/issue_24/MARIIA_Y_TROIAN_NADIYA_M_KOSTYUCHENKOOrganizational_and_Economic_Measures_to_Reform_the_Health_Care_System_in_Ukraine_on_.pdf (In Russian)
11. Movshovich B.L. The medical component of the health potential by the World Health Organization (WHO): time to change the paradigm / B.L. Movshovich // Russian family doctor. – 2010. – Vol. 14, No. 3. – P. 18-19. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/meditsinskaya-sostavlyayuschaya-potentsiala-zdorovya-vsemirnoy-organizatsii-zdravoohraneniya-voz-vremya-smenit-paradigmu/viewer> (In Russian)
12. Risk factors for stroke development according to the register of a large industrial city in Western Siberia: Abstract of the dissert. ... PhD, spec. "Nervous diseases" (14.00.13 according to the Higher Attestation Commission of the Russian Federation) / Yashnikova M.V. - Irkutsk: as a manuscript, 2009. – 201 p. URL: <https://www.dissercat.com/content/factory-riska-razvitiya-insulta-po-dannym-registra-krupnogo-promyshlennogo-goroda-zapadnoi-s/read/pdf> (In Russian)
13. Volgina S.Ya. Fabry disease: Lectures for general practitioners / S.Ya. Volgina // Practical medicine. – 2012. – Vol. 12, No. 07 (Pediatrics). URL: <http://pmarchive.ru/bolezni-fabri> (In Russian)

14. Desnick R.J. Fabry disease, an under-recognized multisystemic disorder: expert recommendations for diagnosis, management, and enzyme replacement therapy / R.J. Desnick, R. Brady, J. Barranger, [et al.] // *Ann Intern Med.* – 2003. – Vol. 138, No.4. – P. 338-346. <https://doi.org/10.7326/0003-4819-138-4-200302180-00014>
15. Fabry disease // US National Library of Medicine. URL: <https://ghr.nlm.nih.gov/condition/fabry-disease>
16. Fabry Disease / A. Mehta, D.A. Hughes; 2002-upd. 2017. In: GeneReviews® [Internet] / ed. M.P. Adam, H.H. Ardinger, R.A. Pagon, [et al.]. – Seattle (WA): University of Washington, 1993-2020. URL: https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK1292/pdf/Bookshelf_NBK1292.pdf
17. Asplund K. Multinational comparisons of stroke epidemiology. Evaluation of case ascertainment in the WHO MONICA Stroke Study / K. Asplund, R. Bonita, K. Kuulasmaa, [et al.] // *Stroke.* – 1995. – Vol. 26, No. 3. – P. 355–360. <https://doi.org/10.1161/01.str.26.3.355>
18. Strunevsky A.V. Modern approaches to the epidemiological monitoring of stroke: the experience of multinational studies / A.V. Strunevsky // *J. of Gr. State Med. Univ.* – 2006. – Vol. 16, No. 4. – P. 76-80. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/sovremennyye-podhody-k-epidemiologicheskomu-monitoringu-insulta-opyt-mnogonatsionalnyh-issledovaniy> (In Russian)
19. Kurtzke J.P. Epidemiology of cerebrovascular disease / J.P. Kurtzke // *Cerebrovascular survey report for National Institute of neurological and communicative disorders and stroke* / Ed. H. Fletcher, McDowell, L.P. Caplan. – Bethesda, 1985. – P. 1-34.
20. Martsevich S.Yu. Analysis of anamnestic factors and their role in determining the closest (hospital) prognosis in patients after a stroke or transient ischemic attack. The results of the register LIS-2 / S.Yu. Martsevich, N.P. Kutishenko, A.Yu. Suvorov // *Russian Journal of Cardiology.* – 2015. – Vol. 122, No. 6. – P. 14-19. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15829/1560-4071-2015-06-14-19> (In Russian)
21. Martsevich S.Yu. Register of acute coronary syndrome LIS-3: what has changed over the years in the “portrait” of the patient and the immediate outcome of the

disease in comparison with the register LIS-1 / S.Yu. Martsevich, Yu.V. Semenova, N.P. Kutishenko, [et al.] // Rational pharmacotherapy in cardiology. – 2017. – Vol. 13, No. 1. – P. 63-68. <http://dx.doi.org/10.20996/1819-6446-2017-13-1-63-68>
(In Russian)

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Региональные регистры инсультов, инфарктов и транзиторных ишемических атак составляются по единому образцу в разных странах мира с 1970х годов. Они позволяют проводить эпидемиологические исследования, изучать факторы риска церебральных инсультов, разрабатывать и корректировать схемы лечения, профилактики и реабилитации пострадавших, проводить проспективные когортные исследования.

Ключевые слова: сердечно-сосудистые заболевания, церебральный инсульт, факторы риска, история изучения инсультов, болезнь Андерсена-Фарби, эпидемиология инсультов.